

A National Observatory's Responsibilities Extend Beyond Telescopes

Michael Blanton, New York University

A national observatory does not just consist of telescopes.

Answering the pressing astronomical and human questions of our time—what are the origins of the Universe? how did galaxies, stars, and planets form? is there life elsewhere?—requires telescope resources beyond what individual universities or private observatories can muster, and they also require much more than the hardware. The most successful modern ground-based astronomical experiments have therefore been those that not only harnessed the resources of large consortia but also maximized their science productivity through early career training, innovative software development, and powerful and user-friendly public data-distribution tools. The Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) has operated this way for over 20 years, coordinating the resources of over 50 individual institutions, and as a result has created the largest spectroscopic maps of our Galaxy, the nearby galaxies, and the Universe as a whole.

Although mid-scale efforts such as SDSS will continue their unique contributions, ground-based astronomy now features billion-dollar-scale efforts, such as Vera C. Rubin

Observatory, that require the size and stability of a national observatory. A wisely designed national observatory can simultaneously leverage its efforts to provide important supporting infrastructure for mid-scale, small-scale, and individual investigator projects. But to replicate the success of current projects on a larger scale, a national observatory needs to provide not just the telescopes but also a system of resources, including training, infrastructure development, human resource development, software products, and data archives, that can support the big efforts and the more moderate ones at the same time.

As just one important aspect of this system, the data sets emerging from Rubin Observatory will require a sophisticated and powerful data-access system. At the same time, mid-scale and small-scale ground-based projects are producing interesting data sets that also need to be archived forever. A well-shepherded effort led by a national observatory would enable an integrated system to archive and distribute the large data sets along with the smaller ones, multiplying their combined value. This national effort could ensure that these archives were maintained over timescales of decades and centuries, living up to the historical tradition set by our astronomical forebears. Similarly, the system of hardware, software, and human resources emerging from national observatory efforts can, if stewarded properly, benefit all of US astronomy.

Furthermore, a national observatory need not and should not be construed as only supporting and archiving projects that happen to be on its own telescopes. We are fortunate in the US to have found philanthropic support for a number of private telescopes, and a national observatory can leverage this support for the benefit of all US astronomers, providing critical infrastructure and encouraging and enabling greater and broader data access over truly long timescales.

A national observatory's responsibilities, therefore, extend beyond the operation of telescopes and beyond the support of projects on its own telescopes. It should lead the country and support all of our ground-based astronomy activities, providing the sort of large-scale, long-term, and community-wide support to them that only a national effort can.